

“Meira Paibis” - The Feminist Icons - A Study

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ABSTRACT

Meira Paibis the ‘women torch bearers’ is a women’s social movement in the Indian state of Manipur. It is one of the largest grassroots movements in the world. Its initial focus of fighting alcoholism and abuse has now expanded to countering human rights violations and the development of society at large. Over the decades, they have led numerous social and political movements in the state, including some powerful protests against alleged atrocities by Indian security forces, leveraging their strong position in society in the interest of the causes they have espoused. As the “guardians of civil society”, Meira Paibis are widely respected and represent a powerful moral force. They may become more visible during certain times, but their presence and importance in Manipur Civil Society are permanent and palpable, and their role as society’s conscience keepers is widely acknowledged. That’s why I have chosen this topic as my research paper. (In this research I have used many books, magazines and news papers as primary and secondary sources for the completion of this paper.)

Key Words: Meira Paibi, Torch Bearers, Grassroot Movement, Guandians of Civil Society, Society’s Conscience Keepers, Powerful Moral force.

Introduction:

“The Manipuri story indicates the active participation by women in public affairs can and does contribute to better conditions for children and society at large”.

-UNICEF

The Peace and Harmony in any Society is a key factor for the growth and development in any country. The People irrespective of gender and age should work together in solving the issues of the society. Since long women in this country were suppressed by male especially in civil society movements. Patriarchy is taken as a reason for female oppression. Because of gender violence, the plight of women in patriarchal society went up to its pathetic and diabolical ebb. The concept of patriarchy leads to the development of many pertinent feminist ideas and programmes. Under these circumstances, the civil society of meira paibis formed from like – minded people consisted of women from different sections with various level of social background. These are individuals with common ideology and goal came together to serve the society across various parts of Manipur. The importance and responsibilities have been increasingly recognized by the society in recent times.

Understanding Of Meira Paibis:

The Meira Paibi, literally translated as ‘Women torch Bearers’ is one such group which plays a pertinent role in the social movement of Manipur, a state in Northeast India became a symbol of resilience fighting against the social evils of the society like drug addiction, Sexual violence and alcoholism. The meira paibis are a group of women particularly belonging to the Meitei community of Manipur who work for the upliftment of the people in the society.

The Meira Paibis, or “Women with Torches”, are Meitei women who are not formally organized and have no political leaning. They become actively only when the

state or society creates any crisis. They yield considerable moral and social influence Among The Meiteis.

Objective:

- ❖ The paper aims to highlight the meira Paibis as feminist icons in Manipur. And examines how this women movement have become a symbol of resilience fighting against the atrocities meted out to individuals in the patriarchal society.
- ❖ The Paper further looks at how meira paibis changed as from guardians to perpetrators of violence with accurate present scenario.

Methodology:

The study adopted an analytical method. For this, the readings of primary, secondary sources, research journals, magazines and online sources gave been taken up.

Findings And Observations:

Meira Paibis as Feminist Icons:

According to Binalakshmi Nepam, author and Manipuri activist, the meira paibis have been active for decades and have taken active role in protesting against the draconian and the contentious Armed Forces Special Powers Act (AFSPA) 1958. Though the current avatar of meira Paibis can be traced to 1977, Women activism in Manipur has a long history.

In 1904, thousands of women came out in protest when British administration forced men between the ages of 17 and 60 to provide free labour for a specified number of days each month. The British had to eventually withdraw the practice. In 1939, Manipuri women stood up against a rise in prices of food items such as rice, This movement was known as Nupi Laan.

In 1977, Women from across all sections of society in Manipur joined hands against growing alcoholism and drug abuse in the state. The movement was launched to curb these social evils. The Movement started an anti-liquor movement called ‘Nisha Bandhis’ which greatly assisted in educating alcoholics and drug addicts about the menace of substance abuse in the same year, women started a mass movement called Meira Paibi movement to maintain peace and social order in Manipur.

On July 11, 2004, the bullet –ridden and badly mutilated body of Thangjam Manorama, 32 Year old Women from Manipur, was found abandoned after she had been arrested by security forces. It was alleged that she had been tortured and raped by soldiers of Assam Rifles five days after, around 12 middle –aged women called Imas (Meitei mothers) stood disrobed themselves and became naked in front of the Assam Rifles office showing placards that read: “Indian Army rape us too,” and “Indian Army take our Flesh” In doing so, they protested against years of discrimination, atrocities, human rights violation and sexual violence.

The twelve mothers courageously challenged the entire nation to the gender violence and human rights violations of women. This became a powerful movement of the Meira Paibi. Such are the brave and stellar acts of the Meira Paibi. A month after this protest, the state government withdrew the controversial AFSPA from 7 Constituencies in Imphal area. The Meira Paibi movement, therefore became a precedent of women empowerment in the patriarchal Manipur Society.

Gender as identity exists because of performing the gendered acts. The gendered performance of the Meira Paibis ranges from being a mother, wife, daughter, daily wage earner, Political activist, Professionals besides being the ‘Meira Paibis’ Yet, they have successfully created a space of a continuous education process.

Their role in the informal education of the society has been tremendous. They have been working relentlessly to cleanse all the evils in the society and even aired

political grievances with the full support of the local youths and elders. And also they work towards an evil free society.

Present Scenario of Meira Paibis from Guardians to Perpetrators of Violence:

Historically, the Meira Paibis have been rather silent about the atrocities conducted by valley-based insurgent groups in the hill districts but the clash between two ethnic groups viz, meities and kuki tribes communities has seemingly transformed the Meira-Paibis into perpetrators of violence against tribal women. Such incidents are not only disheartening when they come from the acclaimed ‘guardians of civil society’.

Several 20 women of kuki tribes were made victims of supposed “revenge rapes”. The shocking revelation of the involvement of meira paibis is not only encouraging their men to rape tribal women but also in physically beating and torturing them has shattered the perception of their role as “Guardians”. This statement is matching with interview of Karan & Thapan two kuki survivors.

Further the women, primarily from the Meitei community burnt down the houses of two accused over a horrific incident where two tribal women were stripped, Paraded and sexually assaulted by a mob of 800 men, alleged from the Meitei community. The incident sparked widespread outrage across the country.

Large-Scale Violence has left at least 100 People dead and displaced more than 60,000 in Manipur since may 3, after clashes broke out between the majority Hindu Meitei community and christian kuki tribes over a government policy that would grant greater benefits to meiteis. Thousands of homes and religious sites, including churches and temples, have been destroyed in the months lunge strife and dozens of cases of sexual assault on women from both communities have emerged. Recently, the Indian Army’s spear corps accused women activist meira paibis in Manipur of deliberately blocking routes and interfering in the operations of security forces as the state struggles to contain weeks of rioting and unrest.

With origins dating back to Indian resistance against British rule, the group see themselves as powerful advocates for peace and fair punishment against violent men from rival ethnic groups.

But their detractors, including the Indian army, say they have taken on the role of vigilantes and are complicating efforts to restore order to the crisis-hit state. As ethnic violence continues to rage after nearly two months in India's north-eastern state of Manipur, a powerful grassroots, women movement known as the "Meira Paibis has taken centre stage-And so, the current violence in Manipur has explicitly shown the undeniable intersection of gender, class, ethnicity and political inclinations in the perpetuation of violence in Manipur region.

One of a Meira Paibi Mrs.Mamta Lukram, Said, "We really feel ashamed that we can't raise our head. We condemned it strongly we feel choked after seeing the viral video. We don't want harassment. We don't want Kuki brethren to commit more crimes we really condemn our Meitei community for committing those kinds of crimes to the women of other communities. It may not be right for us to generalize the whole community through the understanding of a mob. A mob doesn't have a head; they lose their rationality. The prolonged exposure to the conflict situation for more than 75 days without any resolution or ray of hope of resolution, Meitei people are frustrated that they lose their rationality" she said.

Conclusion:

The preceding discussions with a long analysis, the Meira Paibis of Manipur play a crucial role in the states civil society. Their activism spans a range of social and political issues, and they have consistently fought for justice, human rights, and the betterment of society. Despite the recent controversy surrounding their alleged interference in security operations, their contribution as a powerful force for social change should be acknowledged and appreciated. Their iconic protest "was not for Meitei

Women alone, but women across all the 34 tribes of Manipur, adding that meira paibis fight for the women of both communities.

Hence, state and central government have to take a amicable resolution to solve this ethnic clashes through psycho analytical approach by considering the depressed minds of both communities people. Likewise, as per quote of Irom Sharmila, an Indian civil rights activist appeals that all Meiteis and Kuki tribals, to unite, and violence and with Mother nature all Manipuri women use their power to bring back peace.

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